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EFFECT OF TRICHODERMA ON THE QUANTITY AND PRODUCTIVITY OF PHOTOSYNTHETIC PIGMENTS OF COMMON WHEAT (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

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Abstract. We studied the influence micromycete of *Trichoderma asperellum* culture solution on some morphological indicators, photosynthetic pigment quantity and productivity of soft wheat genotype (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivated in the territory of the experimental base station of Kurdamir region of the Republic of Azerbaijan. For this purpose, some of the wheat seeds were soaked with the cultural solution of trichoderma for 15 hours before sowing. It was shown that the morphological indicators such as tillering, root system development, wet and dry weight were higher in the plant treated with trichoderma compared to the control plants. The positive effect of trichoderma was shown in the amount of chlorophyll a, b and carotenoids, as well as in the sign of greenness of the flag leaf. That is, the *Trichoderma asperellum* micromycete increases productivity by stimulating physiological and biochemical processes by joining the metabolism of plants due to the biological agents it synthesizes.

Keywords: *Triticum aestivum*, *Trichoderma asperellum*, photosynthetic pigments, productivity.

ტრიქოდერმის გავლენა ჩვეულებრივი ხორბლის ფოტოსინთეზური პიგმენტების რაოდენობასა და პროდუქტიულობაზე (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

ალადინ გადიმოვი

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კონულ ბახშალიევა

პროფესორი, აზერბაიჯანის რესპუბლიკის მეცნიერებისა და განათლების სამინისტროს მიკრობიოლოგიის ინსტიტუტი, ბაქო, აზერბაიჯანი;

გულნარ მირზაევა

დოქტორანტი, აზერბაიჯანის რესპუბლიკის მეცნიერებისა და განათლების სამინისტროს ბოტანიკის ინსტიტუტი, ბაქო, აზერბაიჯანი.

აბსტრაქტი. შვეისწავლეთ *Trichoderma asperellum* კულტურის ხსნარის მიკრომიცეტის გავლენა ზოგიერთ მორფოლოგიურ მაჩვენებელზე, ფოტოსინთეზური პიგმენტის რაოდენობასა და აზერბაიჯანის რესპუბლიკის ქურდამირის რაიონის ექსპერიმენტული საბაზო სადგურის ტერიტორიაზე კულტივირებული რბილი ხორბლის გენოტიპის (*Triticum aestivum* L.) პროდუქტიულობაზე. ამ მიზნით ხორბლის თესლის ნაწილს თესვამდე 15 საათით ადრე ასველებდნენ ტრიქოდერმის კულტურული ხსნარით. ნაჩვენებია, რომ მორფოლოგიური ინდიკატორები, როგორცაა დარგვა, ფესვთა სისტემის განვითარება, სველი და მშრალი წონა, უფრო მაღალი იყო ტრიქოდერმით დამუშავებულ მცენარეებში საკონტროლო მცენარეებთან შედარებით. ტრიქოდერმის დადებითი ეფექტი გამოვლინდა ქლოროფილის a, b და კაროტინოიდების ოდენობით, აგრეთვე დროშა ფოთლის გამწვანების ნიშნით. ანუ, *Trichoderma asperellum* micromycete ზრდის პროდუქტიულობას ფიზიოლოგიური და ბიოქიმიური პროცესების სტიმულირებით, მცენარეთა მეტაბოლიზმში შეერთებით მის მიერ სინთეზირებული ბიოლოგიური აგენტების გამო.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: *Triticum aestivum*, *Trichoderma asperellum*, ფოტოსინთეზური პიგმენტები, პროდუქტიულობა.

Introduction

Modern agricultural production requires the intensive use of mineral fertilizers and toxic chemicals to protect plants from pests and diseases, so it becomes one of the sources of environmental pollution. Therefore, it is necessary to replace the protection and productivity of plants with alternative methods based on their effect. One of the ecological and resource-efficient ways of the activity and sustainable development of agroecosystems is the application of microbial preparations (both fertilization and plant protection) to modern technologies for growing plants.

The role of soil microorganisms is also great in increasing the resistance of agriculturally important plants to adverse environmental factors and their productivity and quality under stress conditions. In recent years, it should be noted that there has been an increase in work related to the use of micromycetes in this area by world researchers [3, 5]. Some species of fungi are more resistant to drought than bacteria and can reproduce easily under stressful conditions. They spread rapidly in the soil, absorb water and can infect plant tissues. Because fungi can synthesize phytohormones, they can affect the hormonal balance of plants. All these features help them to ensure the resistance of plants against biotic and abiotic stresses [2, 4]. Representatives of the genus *Trichoderma* from this series, in addition to synthesizing phytohormones of natural origin, populate plant roots and protect them from pathogens, stimulate the absorption of nutrients by plants, improve their water-holding capacity and thereby increase their resistance to stress factors, which is why they are the focus of attention of researchers.

The region we have chosen for conducting research differs due to its specific climatic conditions. In addition to high temperatures, there is a shortage of water. The area is mostly saline soils, the amount of humus is below the norm (1.9%), there is a lack of mineral elements (pH-7.9; EC25 -0.67 ms/cm; Carbonation (CaCO_3) -5.9%; Nitrogen (N) -0.062%; Phosphorus (P_2O_5) -28 ppm; Potassium (K) -143 ppm; Calcium (Ca) - 1250 ppm; Magnesium (Mg) -182 ppm; Sodium (Na) -249 ppm; Iron (Fe) - 5.6 ppm; Copper (Cu) -2.2 ppm; Zinc (Zn) -0.8 ppm; Manganese (Mn) -3.7 ppm; Boron (B) -0.075 ppm).

Materials and methods

The local soft Gobustan (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotype of the wheat plant was used as research material. The experiments were planted on the territory of the Karrar Experimental Base Station of the Institute of Botany, located in the Kurdamir region, as an autumn crop. Fertilization was carried out 3 times during planting, during the bushing and spike phases, and irrigation was carried out 2 times at the beginning of bushing and spike. Before sowing, the seeds of the experimental variant were soaked in a culture solution of the fungus *Trichoderma Asperellum* for about 15 hours. The experiments were carried out in 3 replicates with control and experimental (seeds treated with *Trichoderma*). In field conditions, phenological observations were carried out according to Kuperman, starting from germination and ending with the phase of full ripening [6]. The wet and dry biomass of the root and shoot parts of plants was determined during the tillering and tuber formation phases. During the period of physiological maturity, 10 spikelets were selected and the spike elements were determined. After harvesting, the mass of 1000 grains was determined and the yield was calculated based on the grains removed from a unit area. Chlorophylls a, b and carotenoids in leaves were determined spectrophotometrically in 96% ethanol at wavelengths of 664, 648 and 470 nm, respectively, and calculated in mg/g fresh weight [7]. Flag leaf greenness (chlorophyll content) was measured using a SPAD 502 Plus (Konica Minota, Inc., Japan).

Results and their discussion

Analysis of the obtained results and our phenological observations show that the stimulating effect of *Trichoderma* begins with seed germination in the early stages of plant development. Regardless of the plant variety, soaking the seeds in a culture solution of *Trichoderma* led to an increase in their germination and germination strength compared to the plants of the control variant. We have noted the stimulating effect of the micromycete *Trichoderma asperellum* on the length of the above-ground part of wheat and the root system. The length of the aboveground part in the phase of full maturity was 2.9 cm greater than the control in the variant treated with a culture solution of *Trichoderma*. This increase was also reflected in a 51.3% increase in plant biomass compared to the control. In the dry matter collection, this figure was 33.8%.

Based on the number of photosynthetic pigments that play an important role in increasing the productivity of wheat genotypes, one can form an opinion about the level of development of the photosynthetic apparatus, physiological state, potential for formation and harvesting under different growing conditions. Photosynthetic pigments play an important role in increasing the yield of wheat genotypes and are necessary for light harvesting and the production of restorative forces in plants [1].

Tr. asperellum had a positive effect on the assimilation apparatus of the plant; the leaf surface of the plant treated with *trichoderma* was 3.2 cm² larger than that of the control. The increase in leaf area leads to an increase in the photosynthetic efficiency of the plant, which leads to an increase in productivity, which was confirmed in our experiments.

As can be seen from Table 1, due to the action of *Trichoderma*, the amount of chlorophyll a, b and carotenoids increased compared to the control. Compared with the control, the amount of chlorophyll a increased by 2.9%, the amount of b by 4.5%, and the amount of carotenoids by 4.1%. Naturally, this growth was reflected in the Chla+Chlb indicator. A decrease in the Chla+Chlb/Car(x+c) ratio was observed in the *Trichoderma* variant compared to the control (0.59%). This trend continued in the Chla/Clb ratio, 1.51%.

Table 1. Effect of *Trichoderma asperellum* on the amount of photosynthetic pigments of soft Gobustan wheat variety (mg/g wet weight)

Variants	Chla	Chlb	Car(x+c)	Chla+Chlb	Chla+Chlb/ Car(x+c)	Chla/Chlb
Control	7,59502	3,84336	2,51786	11,43838	4,54290	1,97614
Trichoderma	7,81767	4,01643	2,62029	11,8341	4,51633	1,94641

The Gobustan wheat variety treated with *Trichoderma* showed positive results in terms of 1000 grain weight, ear structural elements, biological productivity and grain yield. (table 2.). In plants treated with *Trichoderma*, the weight of 1000 seeds increased by 12% compared to the control variant. Compared with the control, the ear weight increased by 24.6%. As can be seen from Table 2, compared to the control, the length and width of the ear, the number of ears in the ear, the number of grains in the ear and the weight increased.

Table 2. Characterization of grain yield and structural elements of Gobustan wheat variety with the presence of *Trichoderma* (Tr.) micromycete

Variant	Spike		Number of spikes, (by number)	Spake mass, (gr)	Grains		Mass of 1000 grains, gr	Mass of bunch, q	fertilit y gr/m ²
	Lenght, cm	width, cm			Amount (by number)	Mass			
Control	9,56	1,13	15,4	2,48	47,8	1,90	39,8	1395	495
Tr.	11,5	1,32	17,8	3,29	59,2	2,43	44,3	1980	665

Due to the influence of *Trichoderma* on the grain yield formed as a result of the action of the product components, the increase in the yield of Gobustan wheat variety was 25.6% compared to the control.

The obtained results allow us to conclude that *Trichoderma* influences the soil microflora and prevents plant damage by reducing the number of pathogenic microorganisms, and the biological agents synthesized by them stimulate biochemical processes and increase productivity, being included in the metabolism of plants.

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